

An Analysis of Optimal Government Size for Growth: Application of Scully Model in Kenyan Counties

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Abstract

This study, assuming a balanced budget, attempts to estimate the optimal devolved government size in Kenya using the panel ARDL regression and Scully (2008) model for the period 2013-2017. The optimal devolved government size is determined to be around 9.7 percent of the GCP (Gross County Product). The estimated threshold size is higher than the current size of county government which stands at 5.4% of GCP. The panel analysis suggests that the optimal size of government is higher than the current size of government (9.7 > 5.4) and there is a scope of 4.3% increase in county public expenditures. Therefore, the study recommends increase of devolved government spending to arrive at the growth, maximizing level of the government size. This can be possible via increased national government budget allocation to the 47 county government and improved county revenue collection.

Keywords: County government expenditure, optimal government size, devolved expenditure, economic growth

1. Introduction

Africa shows an impressive decentralization institutional creativity. Two countries, Ethiopia and South Africa, have chosen a quasi-federal system. Nigeria, which used to be the only federal state in Africa, has adopted a new constitution that maintains the federal framework and gives more powers to its sub-national governments. In particular, rural areas are receiving priority over the urban ones in the current decentralizing trends in developing countries (Brosio, 2000; KIPPRA, 2016). In a number of countries, such as Kenya, Ethiopia, Mali, Madagascar and Senegal, devolved government, is a response to the demand for more autonomy from some areas of the country, as well as for a more equitable distribution of national shared resources (Brosio, 2000; Mose *et al.*, 2019).

In Kenya, decentralization started as early as 1963, particularly the *Majimbo* system and the sessional paper No 10 of 1965 entitled "African Socialism and its application to planning in Kenya." Further, Mutie (2014) observes that there are four main philosophies that guide fiscal decentralization. These are expenditure responsibilities, intergovernmental fiscal transfers, revenue assignment and sub-national government borrowing. Kenya came up with a new constitution which was promulgated in the year 2010 and fiscal decentralization is integrated in this constitution. Underpinning the devolution agenda was the need to: address deeply entrenched disparities in growth between counties; jumpstart long-term economic growth; improve equity in access to social and economic services at the county level; and, work progressively toward equalizing opportunities for all Kenyans (World Bank, 2014). Before the country prepared a new constitution, fiscal decentralization used to operate at the local authority level as Local Authority Transfer Fund (LATF) (IEA, 2010).

For devolved expenditure, about 20 percent of total government expenditure was spent at sub-national level in 2013/14 for Kenya which is the same level as EAC countries. The share of sub national expenditure closely mimics the levels in the region; in Uganda and Tanzania expenditure by sub-national governments account for 20 and 22 percent

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(respectively); while in Ethiopia it accounts for 46 percent of total spending. The share of devolved funds traditionally is higher in federal countries, with Nigeria, Brazil, South Africa and Ethiopia as examples (IEA, 2010; World Bank, 2014; SID, 2017; GoK, 2018).

Fiscal policy is one of the government policies that influence economic activities by raising the revenue through taxation and control of the level of expenditure (Muguro, 2017). The Keynes theory presents the multiplier effect and argues that the increase in county government expenditure will increase demand and thus increases county GCP growth (Mutie, 2014). Fiscal policy settings can affect output and economic growth in the medium term as well as over the business cycle. However, the county spending action to the economic growth may be beneficial and at the same time be detrimental (Husnain, 2011). Table 1 shows the trend of GCP growth and government size growth from 2013 to 2017.

Table 1: Government Size in Kenya

YEAR	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Real GCP growth rate - (%)	5.9	5.4	5.7	5.9	4.9
National Expenditure - (% GCP)	23.7	25.9	26.6	25.3	24.6
County Expenditure - (% GCP)	4.3	5.4	5.4	5.3	5.3

Source: KIPPRA (2016); GoK (2018); KNBS (2019).

From Table 1 above, there is evidence that the size of government has been rising. However, the growth of government size is that of double digit while GCP is growing at a single digit. This can be attributed to increasing county wage bill over the years (OCOB, 2017). In addition, from Table 1, county expenditure as a percentage of GCP was low in comparison to national government expenditure as a percentage of GCP in Kenya during the periods 2013-2017. Specifically, county and national government size has been increasing gradually from 4.3 and 23.7 percent as a share GCP in 2013 to 5.3 and 24.6 percent of GCP in 2017, respectively. During the same period, the rate of growth of GCP was cyclical, depicting no clear pattern and responsiveness to changes in both government sizes (KIPPRA, 2016). Despite the widespread government strategies to foster economic expansion, increase in county government expenditure has tended to grow faster than that of GCP. The trends in this Table 1 reveal a widening gap between county government size and county economic growth and therefore a concern that this study is interested in.

1.1. Problem Statement

While devolved expenditure, in general, is necessary to have a county economy capable of operating correctly as well in order to foster the income growth, its continuous expansion cannot be assumed to be consistent with the long-run maximization of economic growth. Indeed, increase in devolved government expenditure implies an increased tax burden, which may hamper growth, or a deficit that may increase public debt with an increased cost of its service and an obstacle to the county growth. Nevertheless, even if it is true that beyond a given limit, public expenditure may reduce economic growth, it may also improve the quality of GCP. A high rate of growth accompanied by a too unequal distribution of resources could conflict with the objective of maximizing general county welfare. In Kenya, economic growth has been fluctuating, depicting no clear pattern and responsiveness to changes in government size, despite the devolved expenditure increasing over time (KNBS, 2019). Therefore, there is need to determine the optimal county government size for policy recommendations.

1.2. Objective

To determine whether there is optimal county government size in Kenya.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

Optimal county government size does not exist in Kenya.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Optimal Government Size

Armey (1995); and Scully (2003) did theoretical and empirical research and popularized the existence of an optimal size of government as depicted by an inverted U-curve. As government continues to grow as a share of the economy, expenditures are channelled into less productive (and later counterproductive) activities, causing growth to diminish and eventually decline (Vedder & Gallaway, 1998; Leach, 2002; Barro & Sala-i, 2003; Mose *et al.*, 2019).

Notes: g – Real Gross County Product (Proxy for Economic Growth)

E – Equilibrium

CGE – County Government Expenditure (Proxy for Government Size)

T – Time variable

Figure 1: Armey Curve (Source: Armey (1995); Leach (2002); Scully (2003))

Explanations for this trend can be found in the decrease of private investments due to the 'crowding-out' effect, higher tax rates and less free market. Additionally, the Armey Curve indicates an optimal size of the government E^* , where maximum economic growth is reached. At this point, an increasing amount of public expenditure leads to a decrease of economic growth. This point differs country by country and may rely on economic factors like openness of the economy as well as social factors like population size (Armey, 1995; Leach, 2002).

The Arme y Curve can be expressed in a simple quadratic form, as follows:

$$(g_{i,t}) = \alpha + \beta(CGE)_{it} + \delta(CGE)^2_{it} + \gamma T \quad 1$$

The positive sign on the linear term, CGE, is designed to show the beneficial effects of government spending on economic expansion, while the negative sign for the squared term means the variable measures any adverse effects associated with increased government size. Since the squared term increases in value faster than the linear term, the presence of negative effects from government spending eventually will outweigh the positive effect, producing downward-sloping portion of the Arme y Curve (Arme y, 1995; Leach, 2002; Wanjuu *et al.*, 2017). To control for factors unrelated to government spending, Vedder and Gallaway (1998) introduced the time variable (T). Therefore, the faster and greater the expenditure increases, the greater the probability of diminishing returns and ineffective use.

2.2 The Arme y Curve Quadratic Equation

In order to test the relationship between County Government Expenditures (CGE) and economic growth that is theoretically characterized by the inverted U curve, this study uses a simple quadratic equation following Arme y (1995); Vedder and Gallaway (1998); Facchini and Melki (2013); and Wanjuu *et al.* (2017).

$$(GCP_{i,t}) = a + b(CGE)_{it} + c(CGE)^2_{it} \quad 2$$

The (CGE) which guarantees the optimal level of county economic growth (GCP) is derived by taking the first derivative of the equation (2) in respect to CGE and then equated to zero.

$$\frac{\partial GCP}{\partial CGE} = b + 2(c)CGE_{i,t} \quad 3$$

Equating equation 3 to zero gives the optimum government size percentage.

$$CGE = -\frac{b}{2c} \quad 4$$

2.3 The Scully Model

Scully (2003); and Scully (2008) developed a model that estimates the share of county government spending (or general tax rate) that maximizes real economic growth. According to the Scully model, both the public as well as private sectors contribute to the gross domestic product in counties. Public sector provides goods and services which are financed with tax collections from the population. This becomes the public sector spending. On the other hand, the private people give taxes to government and fraction of the rest of their income is saved which in turn is used to produce goods and services. The fraction of income of the private people given to the county government is given by;

$$\frac{T}{Y} = \tau$$

where T is total taxes and τ is the associated tax rate and Y is the GDP. Or in other words, τ is the share of county public sector in GDP. The share of the private sector in GDP is “1- τ ”. (1- τ) is the share of the income of the people left with them after taxation which leads to the production of goods and services. The functional form of this relationship is given by the following Cobb-Douglas production form as;

$$Y_{it} = \gamma \left(\frac{G}{Y}\right)^\alpha (1 - \tau)^\beta \quad 5$$

α and β are the shares of the public and private sectors respectively. Equation (5) is a nonlinear production. Y is GDP and G is county government expenditure. ' τ ' shows the ratio of tax to GDP and ' γ ' shows total factor productivity. The log transformation of equation (5) is given by;

$$\ln Y_{it} = \ln \gamma + \alpha \ln \left(\frac{G}{Y} \right) + \beta \ln (1 - \tau) \quad (6)$$

This is simplified as follows;

$$\alpha \left(\frac{Y}{G} \right) \left(\frac{1}{Y} \right) = \alpha G^{\beta-1}$$

Now taking second derivative with respect to G , thus get;

$$\frac{\partial^2 \ln Y}{\partial G^2} = -\alpha G^{-2}$$

This exercise shows that the value of the first derivative is positive while the second derivative is negative as is shown by the negative sign of the second derivative. This shows that public expenditure affects growth positively but the magnitude of this effect decreases over the time i.e it affects economic growth at decreasing rate afterward. This results into non-linear relationship between expenditure and growth (Scully, 2003; Husnain, 2011).

3. Methodology

This study employed historical research design so as to capture the trend of county economic growth and government expenditure in Kenya. This was carried out in the period 2013 - 2017 using annual series secondary data for 47 counties and panel ARDL technique, resulting in 235 county-year observations. This study was carried out in Kenya. This is because in the study period, there has been a significant transfer of funds to 47 county governments by the national government in order to address disparities in country growth.

The data was from previous publications which could only be sourced from secondary sources. The study utilized annual data from Statistical abstracts, Economic surveys, Gross County Product report and County Budget Implementation Review Reports.

3.1 Panel Data Analysis Techniques

Building on previous studies (Facchini & Melki, 2013; Mose *et al.*, 2019), a simple growth panel model was formulated from equation (7).

$$\ln Y_{i,t} = \beta \ln X_{i,t-1} + \gamma \ln G_{i,t-1} + \mu_i + v_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

Where, $\ln Y_{i,t}$ - the dependent variable-County economic growth

$\ln X_{i,t-1}$ - set of explanatory variables apart from devolved county expenditure

$\ln G_{i,t-1}$ - the county devolved government expenditure variables

β and γ - are parameters to be estimated

μ_i - county fixed effects v_t - time fixed effects $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ - the error term

and the subscripts i and t represent county and time period respectively

To achieve objective, this study followed Scully (2008); and ARDL model that explains the level of government size (G) in a county economy and the corresponding level of economic growth. ARDL model is applicable irrespective of whether the underlying variables are I(0) or I(1) and applicable for small sample size estimation (Narayan & Smyth, 2005).

Thus, equation 7 was reformulated as a panel ARDL model, to determine the underlying relationship between dependent and independent variables, to obtain models (8) below.

$$\Delta \ln Y_{i,t} = \sum_{i=1}^k \beta \Delta \ln X_{i,t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma \Delta \ln G_{i,t-1} + \mu_i + v_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (8)$$

Now to find the optimal level of government size, this study follow Scully (2008); and Heerden (2008) to impose the restriction of a balance budget of the counties, that is ($G = T$). So to impose this balanced budget restriction the tax rate is given by;

$\frac{G}{Y} = \tau$ now is called the anticipated tax rate. Where G is government spending and Y is GDP. Or in other words, τ is the share of county public sector in GDP. The share of the private sector in GDP is “ $1 - \tau$ ”. ($1 - \tau$) is the share of the income of the people left with them after taxation which leads to the production of goods and services. The functional form of this relationship is given by the following Cobb-Douglas production form as;

$$Y_{it} = \gamma \left(\frac{G}{Y} \right)^\alpha (1 - \tau)^\beta \quad (9)$$

α and β are the shares of the public and private sectors respectively. Equation (9) is a nonlinear production. Y is GCP and G is county government expenditure. ‘ τ ’ shows the ratio of tax to GCP and ‘ γ ’ shows total factor productivity. The log transformation of equation (9) is given by;

$$\ln Y_{it} = \ln \gamma + \alpha \ln \left(\frac{G}{Y} \right) + \beta \ln (1 - \tau) \quad (10)$$

Now substitute ‘ $\frac{G}{Y} = \tau$ ’ into equation (10), thus get;

$$\ln Y_{it} = \ln \gamma + \alpha \ln \tau + \beta \ln (1 - \tau) \quad (11)$$

So to find growth maximizing level of government size, this study differentiates equation (11) w.r.t ‘ τ ’. After differentiation then;

$$\frac{\partial \ln Y}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial \alpha \ln \tau}{\partial \tau} - \frac{\partial \beta \ln (1 - \tau)}{\partial \tau} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\alpha}{\tau} - \frac{\beta}{1 - \tau} = 0$$

Solving for “ τ ” (the optimal tax rate), this study get $\beta \tau = \alpha (1 - \tau)$, and finally,
 $\tau^* = \alpha / (\alpha + \beta)$

In order to provide intuitive interpretation of the findings obtained from this study, several post estimation panel diagnostic tests were conducted.

4.0 Results

The panel ARDL regression results are reported in Table 2 given below.

Table 2: Optimal Devolved Expenditure Regression Result (SBC - 1, 0, 0)

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t- Statistics	P-value
$\ln y(-1)$	0.842831***	0.033217	25.37367	0.0000
$\ln \tau$	0.152954***	0.032901	4.648914	0.0000
$\ln (1 - \tau)$	1.422697**	0.601285	2.366096	0.0188
<i>Cons</i>	0.995023***	0.171124	5.814626	0.0000
LM Test	F = 0.988767		Prob > F = 0.4147	
Breusch - Pagan Test	F = 8.876056***		Prob > F = 0.0000	
Pesaran CD	z = -1.156541		Pr = 0.2475	

Ramsey-Reset Test	F = 1.818203	Pr = 0.1789
Goodness of Fit Test	F statistics = 226.6525***	P-value(F)= 0.0000
Goodness of Fit Test	R ² = 0.747241	Adjusted R ² = 0.743944

*Notes: *** significant at 1%, ** significant at 5%, all the absolute values of the variables are expressed in natural log. $\ln Y_{it}$ – County real GCP (economic growth), $\ln \tau$ – devolved expenditure (recurrent + capital), $1 - \tau$ – share of the private sector in GCP.*

The above results of the equation for the optimal size of the government show that all the variables have carried out significant coefficients as shown by high “t” statistics.

$$\ln Y_{it} = 0.995023 + 0.152954 \ln \tau + 1.422697 \ln (1 - \tau) \quad (13)$$

To calculate the optimal county government size, this study use equation (11). So substitute the values of “ α ” and “ β ” from the above in equation (13), then getting;

$$\tau = \frac{0.152954}{0.152954 + 1.422697} * 100 = 9.7 \quad (14)$$

The optimal size of the devolved government size (both capital and recurrent) is found to be around 9.7 percent of the GCP as is shown by the above empirical analysis against actual 5.4 percent of GCP in 2017. This reflects a reduction in public spending over the optimal target. On the other hand, actual average size of the government spending is 5.4 percent for 2015-2017 (KIPPRA, 2016; SID, 2017). The optimum government size was low considering counties only receive 15% of total revenue from national government. This finding is very much interesting since it highlights that the current size of county government in Kenya is below the optimum level or size and there is still scope of increase in devolved government spending to the GCP ratio in Kenya. Further, about 20 percent of total government expenditure was spent at sub-national level in 2013/14 which is the same level as East African Community countries. The share of devolved funds traditionally is higher in federal countries, with Nigeria, Brazil and Ethiopia (World Bank, 2014; OCOB, 2014; GoK, 2016). The finding of this study fits into Obben (2013) study which found 7.4% of GDP for OECD countries, including Kenya. In contrast, Legge (2015) did not find any optimum government size in the countries (DCs and LDCs) studied.

From the result on Table 2 above, cross-sectional dependence and autocorrelation were not a problem in this study. However, heteroscedasticity was a problem but the study used panel robust standard error to correct it. Also, the adjusted R² was 0.74 implying that 74 percent of the variations of the dependent variable are explained by the explanatory variables in the model. This indicated that the overall goodness of fit was satisfactory.

Recommendations and Areas for further study

This study recommends devolved expenditure is increased by county government from 5.4% to 9.7% of GCP. This is possible through increased national government budget allocation to counties and improved county revenue collection. In addition, for Ethiopia, it accounts for 46.0 per cent of total expenditure, probably because it has been implementing devolution for longer than Kenya. Thus, Kenya has room to improve budget allocation to be in the same league with her peers like Ethiopia. Fixing the share of government expenditures in counties with the optimum government size (9.7% of GCP), this recommendation can guarantee high and stable economic growth. The low level of government size in counties reflects the low level of economic growth in Kenya.

In future studies, macroeconomic analysis should be extended to include a more detailed disaggregation of county government expenditures by functions. Such a disaggregation would allow extension of the analysis and distinguish among the optimal size of devolved recurrent spending, capital expenditure and human expenditure on county economic growth.

References

- Armey, R. D. (1995). *The Freedom Revolution*. Washington DC, Rognery Publisher.
- Barro, R., & Sala-i, M. X. (2nd ed.) (2003). *Economic Growth*. Cambridge, MIT press.
- Facchini, F., & Melki, M. (2013). Efficient Government Size in France. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 31, 1-14.
- GOK (Government of Kenya). (2004- 2019). *Economic surveys*. Nairobi, Kenya National Bureau of Statistics.
- Heerden, Y. V. (2008). Finding the Optimal level of Taxes in South Africa: A Balanced Budget Approach. Department of Economics, *Working Paper*.
- Husnain, M. I., (2011). Is the Size of Government Optimal in Pakistan: A Time Series Analysis, 1975-2008. *Journal of Economics & Economic Education Research* 12(2).
- Husnain, M. I., Khan, M., Haq Padda, I., Akram, N., & Haider, A. (2011). Public Spending, FDI and Economic Growth: A Time Series Analysis for Pakistan (1975-2008). *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 61, 21–27.
- IEA (Institute of Economic Affairs). (2010). Devolution in Kenya, Prospects, challenges and the future. *IEA Research paper*, series No.24.
- Iftikhar, M. (2011). Is the Size of Government Optimal in Pakistan: A Time Series Analysis? 1975-2008. *Journal of Economics and Economic Education Research*, 12(2), 41-49.
- Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS). (2019). *Gross County Product Report 2019*, Nairobi.
- KIPPRA. (2016). *Kenya Economic Report: Fiscal Decentralization in Support of Devolution*, Nairobi.
- Leach, G. (2002). We are going the Wrong Way-Tax and Spending Fiscal Policy. *IoD Policy Paper*, London.
- Legge, S. (2015), *Government Size and Economic Growth: The Role of Country Diversity*. Available from: <http://www.spring2015-201520103017pdf>. (Accessed on 7/12/2016)

- Mose, N., Kibet, L., & Kiprop, S. (2019). The effect of county government expenditure on Gross County Product in Kenya: A panel data analysis. *African Journal of Business Management*, 13(13), 428-437
- Muguro, W.J. (2017). *Effect of Public Expenditure on Economic Growth in Kenya: 1963-2015*. Master's thesis, KCA University, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Mutie, N. (2014). *Effects of Devolved Funds on Economic Growth in Kenya: Empirical Investigation (1993-2012)*. Master's thesis, University of Nairobi, Nairobi.
- Narayan, P.K., & Smyth, R. (2005). The residential demand for electricity in Australia: an application of the bounds testing approach to cointegration. *Energy Policy*, 33, 457–464.
- Obben, J. (2013). Aspects of the Government Size-Economic Growth Rate Nexus in the OECD: 1973-2011. Massey University *Discussion Paper*, 13.04, Palmerstone, New Zealand
- OCOB (Office of the Controller of Budget). (2013-2019). *Annual County Governments Budget Implementation Review Report*. Nairobi, Government Printer.
- Olaleye, S., Femi, E., Bello, T., & Taiwo, B. (2014). Government Expenditure and Economic Growth: Armey Curve in Nigeria. *The Romanian Economic Journal*, 17(51), 47-66.
- Scully, G. (2003). Optimal taxation, economic growth and income inequality. *Public Choice*, 115, 299–312.
- Scully, G. (2008). Optimal Taxation, Economic Growth and Income Inequality in the United States. National Center for Policy Analysis, *Policy Report No. 316*.
- Shumaila, Z., & Abdul, Q. (2014). An Analysis of Optimal Government Size for Growth: A Case Study of Pakistan. Pakistan Institute of Development Economics. *MPRA Paper No. 58989*
- SID (Society for International Development) (2017) Taxation and fiscal decentralisation in Kenya; a case study of Kwale, Kiambu and Kisumu Counties. *Working Paper No. 3*.
- Vedder, K., & Gallaway, E. (1998). *Government Size and Economic Growth*. Washington, Ohio University press.
- Wanjuu Z, L., Khobai, H., & Pierre, R. (2017). Government Size and Economic Growth in Africa and the

OECD. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*,7(4), 628-637.

World Bank. (2014). Decision Time: Spend More or Spend Smart? Decision Time: Spend More or Spend Smart? *Working paper*, No. 94021, Nairobi.